

eResearch NZ / eRangahau Aotearoa – The Case for Open Source in the Science System of Aotearoa

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Introduction

At the 2025 eResearch NZ / eRangahau Aotearoa conference in Christchurch, Jonah Duckles and Richard Littauer held a birds-of-a-feather (BoF) workshop on “The Case for Open Source in Aotearoa (a continuing conversation)”. This was a follow-up to the BoF at the eResearch NZ 2024 conference. The format was a one-hour discussion. Participants passed the mic around, and discussed: (1) The barriers to open source adoption in Aotearoa New Zealand; (2) The opportunities for future growth; and (3) The immediate things a researcher can do to support Open Source Software (OSS) in New Zealand. Below, we share the main points that were covered in this discussion.

OSS plays a critical role in the global technology ecosystem. It fosters collaboration, transparency, and innovation, providing a foundation for modern computing and research. There was a clear view from participants that Aotearoa New Zealand does not have incentives for open source currently, particularly within Crown Research Institutes (CRIs), and no clear policies in the science funding system encouraging open source. This is despite Aotearoa New Zealand’s past role in open source software projects that have significant international impact, such as the R programming language, the Weka machine learning toolkit, and BEAST.

In Aotearoa New Zealand, open source has the potential to empower local industries, academia, and government by promoting digital sovereignty, cost-effective solutions, and knowledge-sharing. Open source is used worldwide to share work on non-competitive pieces of critical software infrastructure for both industry and science.

By not building skills and practices around open source, New Zealanders are at a disadvantage in the broader global science ecosystem where open source practices are embedded in working modes and funder expectations. While Aotearoa New Zealand has made important and notable contributions in the Open Source movement, integrating open source methodologies and incentivising its use in the sciences lags behind global peers.

Barriers to Open Source Adoption and Contribution

Despite its advantages, open source faces significant hurdles that hinder both individual and institutional participation. These challenges include:

1. Lack of Time and Recognition

Many contributors struggle to find time to improve, maintain, or even engage with open source projects. Software development, particularly in academia and research institutions, prioritises publications over code contributions. Without formal recognition or incentives, researchers and developers often find it difficult to justify their involvement in OSS. There are some avenues to change this, such as the [RSE-AUNZ](#), which aims to help highlight the work and value of research software engineers. However, these are still relatively niche, and not all open source is written as part of a dedicated research software position.

Finally, it can be difficult to find open source work that originates in Aotearoa New Zealand, as opposed to just being used here. When Aotearoa New Zealand projects are mentioned, the most charismatic are frequently the only examples – for example, the R language. Other maintainers and coders who work on fundamental digital infrastructure in Aotearoa New Zealand may not have their work recognised locally.

2. Funding and Sustainability Issues

Open source projects frequently suffer from a lack of ongoing funding and institutional support. Many government-funded initiatives are required to commercialise their outputs, making open source licensing difficult. Administrations that effectively require quick wins and outputs may not see the long-term benefit of building a collaborative ecosystem, and may not be placed to collect on any possible gains.

Additionally, open source maintainers themselves face pressure to sustain orphaned projects without adequate compensation, leading to burnout and stagnation. Many open source projects in Aotearoa New Zealand start in academia, where frequent turnover, graduation, and shifting research priorities lead to abandoned open source products that lack open source maintainers.

One problem which is not unique to Aotearoa New Zealand is brain drain; software careers are expensive, and there is often more funding available overseas. As well as individuals making their way to foreign markets under their own steam, large corporations may have satellite offices locally in Aotearoa New Zealand with the purpose of headhunting local talent and moving it abroad. Retaining talented open source developers is difficult.

3. Challenges in Collaboration and Accessibility

Writing universally applicable code is challenging, and ensuring accessibility for diverse users requires additional effort. Poor implementations, frequent upgrades, and inconsistent documentation can create confusion, making it harder for new contributors to engage with projects.

Reproducibility for academic code is important, as it enables peer review and trust that the code is doing what the documentation states it is doing. Code is often not written to be reproducible from the start. Backporting code to become reproducible later is difficult. Writing code while keeping in mind best practices around reproducibility leads to better science in the long run, but the gap between knowing the best practices and implementing them can be large.

Writing good code also requires significant mentorship and collaboration, which can be difficult to find in a stressed academic environment. Support networks are often international—requiring waking up at odd times of the night, for instance—or only targeted at specific labs or universities, and rarely have buy-in from CRI senior leadership. Support can also come in different forms, from either talent coming from industry or mentors, treasure in terms of fiscal sponsorship, or allocating time to development on open source work. With open source in particular, infrastructure can be considered a fourth form of support, as support can enable open source projects to run on funded infrastructure (for instance, like an HPC cluster).

Existing support often comes tied to specific uses, such as in HPC. This specificity may also limit the scope of what people think is possible open source, as non-HPC code may not be considered valuable enough to open. In this sense, digital humanities work or niche coding projects may not benefit from the same support as shinier domains like genomics or health data. Funding schemes that leave out swathes of the research population, such as the [Marsden Fund](#)

and the [Health Research Council](#) (the two major sources of fully-costed non-MBIE research funding in NZ), may ignore open source practitioners working in less-advertised fields, such as digital humanities.

4. Institutional and Governmental Barriers

Conflicting government policies complicate open source adoption. While some agencies encourage transparency, others impose restrictions due to data sensitivity, commercialization mandates, or rigid procurement policies. Universities and research institutions provide little recognition for open source contributions, providing limited recognition for academic career progression.

Additionally, the current CRI mergers caused by the formation of Public Research Organisations (PROs) and the coalition government's large-scale trimming of the academic and social sector has made it difficult to push through open source policies in research. Open source is often seen as supplementary to other work. Institutional support takes time, effort, and capacity that comes most easily in institutions which have both secure funding channels and more resiliency against fluctuating government or industrial support. Further, the policies that depend upon financially backing every research decision incentivise short-term goals such as selling software or keeping priority knowledge in-house, and disincentivising fruitful collaborations that take time and effort.

5. Cultural and Structural Resistance

Organisations and IT departments are often reluctant to adopt open source solutions due to familiarity with proprietary systems and concerns about long-term support. The "free-rider" problem—where entities use OSS without contributing back—exacerbates sustainability issues. Additionally, many institutions lack the necessary knowledge or expertise to implement open source effectively. There is also a perception that OSS is less secure and may expose organisations to increased risk.

Open source as a licensing policy is not always easy to navigate, and research offices or tech transfer offices may not always have in-house knowledge on what license to use, or may not hold

adequate workshops and knowledge facilitation sessions to their staff explaining how to implement open source in their work.

Opportunities for Open Source in Aotearoa New Zealand

Despite these challenges, Aotearoa New Zealand has significant opportunities to leverage and grow its open source ecosystem.

1. Building Awareness and Recognition

Encouraging developers and researchers to document and share their work through platforms such as source code forges (GitHub, GitLab, Bitbucket etc), social media (Mastodon, Bluesky, LinkedIn etc.), and personal blogs with appropriate open licenses can increase visibility and recognition. Formalising citations for open source contributions in academic research could provide additional incentives. Encouraging contested funded projects to openly share source code should also be considered by funders.

There has been work in the past focused on open source in Aotearoa New Zealand: for instance, the [New Zealand Open Source Society](#) has done work promoting it within the country. Further, Catalyst and other companies have funded the Ngā Tohu Pūmanawa Herekore o Aotearoa / [NZ Open Source Awards](#), which has given awards to the best open source projects every other year on average. Other societies like PythonNZ continue to hold meaningful conferences which champion open source projects. This work is excellent, but it is often happening only in industry, and is not as prevalent in the eResearch sector.

2. Sustainable Funding and Support Mechanisms

A dedicated fund for promising open source projects could provide critical support for maintainers. Government agencies, universities, and industry stakeholders could collaborate to establish long-term funding models, ensuring continued development and maintenance of open source projects.

There is an opportunity for this to be implemented as part of the proposed PROs; if PRO leadership work together to put their work in the commons, some efforts can be deduplicated, easing the load on a tumultuous research system.

3. Leveraging Open Source for Economic and Digital Sovereignty

Aotearoa New Zealand can position itself as a hub for open source development by fostering an ecosystem that benefits both local and international users. Case studies such as SQLite, OpenJS, and The Carpentries show how open source projects can sustain themselves through consulting, training, and support services rather than software sales.

In the current global political climate, quick policy wins could involve divesting from foreign digital infrastructures that may be deemed to be unreliable or untrustworthy. Ultimately, digital sovereignty as a concept is antithetical to open source, in that it relies upon a worldview where each country is an island shoring up its own data, providers, and code. However, it still allows a seat at the table for how to best invest and support local talent. This can also be a talking point to offset local brain drain; with many talented engineers working abroad, focusing on bringing smart New Zealanders back to work in industry here can offer a competitive advantage.

For example, the change in American political interests has led many Europeans to consider digital sovereignty as a bolster to open source efforts. The [Sovereign Tech Agency](#) has allocated millions to open source projects. The German and French governments have also worked together to produce an open source alternative to Google Docs, called [Docs](#).

4. Strengthening Collaboration and Community Building

Establishing open source working groups, meetups, and online forums can facilitate knowledge-sharing and community engagement. Creating a national registry of open source projects would help developers and organisations find, contribute to, and promote local OSS initiatives. [One registry](#) of over 30,000 open source developers associated with Aotearoa New Zealand is a good start, but we call for more story-telling and shared spaces for developers to meet and work with each other.

5. Policy and Institutional Support

Government policies that mandate or encourage open source adoption can drive broader participation. For instance, requiring open-source-first procurement strategies or recognizing open source contributions in academic evaluation frameworks could significantly boost engagement.

Actionable Steps Forward

Several immediate steps that can be taken today came up through the conversation:

As an Individual Software Developer and Researcher

The first step is to license your own software as open source, and share it widely under that license. This part seems obvious, but can be difficult to remember to do. Sites like choosealicense.com can be used to find the appropriate license for your work.

Second, scope set when you build your open source software. Decide what you will commit to doing in the long haul, and publicly write in the documentation what you are available for in terms of support. This can be important for learning how to sunset or handover a project to the next maintainer.

Add a [Citation.CFF](#) file to your repository. This will enable your work to become an easily citable object that will allow other researchers to cite it. Add your work to your ORCID account, and place it prominently on your website where your research is normally listed.

If your online profile has an option to add your country—for instance, as GitHub does—add Aotearoa New Zealand. This may enable you to be seen by others, and will highlight the work as a whole.

As a community member

Your work will go farther if you help others. Find your local RSE groups at your university, or your local working groups on sharing technical knowledge. Your research office, school, or library may also have resources. If you are at a CRI/PRO, see if there is anyone who is interested in holding sessions on sharing code.

The Research Software Alliance (ReSA) has [guidelines](#) and [software policies](#) which are a resource for building community of RSEs, and for funding and resourcing research software

projects. While research software is not exactly the same as open source, they are both part of the open science movement, and best practices for one are often applicable to the other.

There are also often regional groups interested in open source. These could be by language—for instance, PythonNZ has events in Auckland and Wellington. Local meetups may be a good way to talk about open source opportunities and to share your research.

As a policy maker or administrator

Support your teams by providing them with resources on how to share their code locally. This may involve allocating space for them to work together on open source, as well as sharing metaknowledge such as how to appropriately license their work for maximum impact.

Work on policies that explicitly honor and recognise open source practitioners. Recognition is important for software engineers. Talking about their work may help, as will building institutional policies that encourage and reward meaningful shared code in themselves.

Talk to other PROs and establishments about building in feedback loops where open tooling is rewarded. If there are any success stories, share them widely.

There are resources for funders who are interested in providing support for open source and research software, such as ReSA resources shared above. Other philanthropic funders have also invested in the space - for instance, the Alfred P. Sloan foundation [has funded](#) over a dozen open source programme offices (OSPOs) in universities, and has provisioned them with a community that is meant to support collaborative efforts between institutions ([CURIOSS](#)). Reach out to ReSA and CURIOSS for guidance on how to best collaborate and support open source in the sciences.

Conclusion

Addressing barriers such as lack of time, funding, and institutional support requires coordinated efforts from government, academia, and industry. By fostering a collaborative open source ecosystem, Aotearoa New Zealand can strengthen its technological landscape.

This white paper highlights key barriers and opportunities for open source in Aotearoa New Zealand. Further research and community discussions will be essential in identifying actionable strategies for growth and sustainability.